
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FAMILY IN THE SOCIALIZATION OF THE INDIVIDUAL.

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Annotation.

The article attempts to show the role and importance of the family in shaping the personality of the child. And also in the article the microclimate of the family, love and mutual understanding are considered. The author reveals the role of the family in the socialization of the individual in modern society. The communicative and behavioral-activity components are also considered, which help in the formation of the child's self-awareness.

Key words.

family, formation, socialization, upbringing, family microclimate, emotional development of the child.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СЕМЬИ В СОЦИОЛИЗАЦИИ ЛИЧНОСТИ.

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Аннотация.

В статье предпринята попытка показать роль и значение семьи в формировании личности ребёнка. А также в статье рассматривается микроклимат семьи, любовь и взаимопонимания. Автор раскрывает роль семьи в

социализации личности в современном обществе. Так же рассматривается коммуникативный и поведенческо – деятельностные компоненты, которые помогает в становление самосознания ребенка .

Ключевые слова.

семья, формирования, социализация, воспитания, семейный микроклимат, эмоционального развития ребёнка.

The family plays an important role in shaping a person's personality. Raising your child is a great art, since the process of education itself is a continuous work of the heart, mind and will of the parents. The comprehensive upbringing of the child, preparing him for life in society is the main social task solved by society and the family.

Parents are the first educators and teachers of the child, so their role in shaping his personality is enormous. In everyday communication with parents, the baby learns to know the world, imitates adults, gains life experience, learns the norms of behavior. Parents have to look every day for ways to approach the child, to think about resolving many specific situations put forward by life, but it is not always possible to find the right solution. In difficult cases, parents turn to the teacher for advice. Educators of preschool institutions are well aware of the patterns of development of a child of preschool age, the methods of his upbringing and do everything possible to assist parents in mastering the basics of pedagogical knowledge. In conversations with parents about the role of family education, the teacher emphasizes how many-sided the influence of parents on the emerging personality: talks about the style of relations of all family members, about the orientation of their interests and its needs, creating an appropriate moral microclimate [1].

The effectiveness of pedagogical influences largely depends on the family microclimate: a child is more amenable to educational influences if he grows up in an atmosphere of mutual sympathy. If benevolence and love reign in the child's family, this works as a positive factor and, conversely, children with mental disorders and personality problems grow up in an atmosphere of cold alienation and constant conflicts. It is in the family that the interests, needs and value orientations of the child are first formed. The influence of the family microclimate on the formation of a person's personality is great. The family is the school of the child's feelings. Observing the relationships of adults, their emotional reactions and feeling the whole variety of manifestations of the feelings of people close to him,

the child acquires moral and emotional experience. In a calm environment, the baby is calm, he has a sense of security, emotional balance.

The child is active and inquisitive by nature, he easily absorbs everything he sees and hears around, the mood of adults is transmitted to him. It is important what emotional impressions he receives: positive or negative; what manifestations of adults he observes: cordiality, caring, tenderness, friendly faces, calm tone, humor or fuss, nervousness, grouchiness, envy, pettiness, gloomy faces. All this is a kind of alphabet of feelings - the first brick in the future building of personality [2].

A family is a collective whose members are interconnected by certain responsibilities. Being a member of the family team, the child also enters into a system of existing relationships, thanks to which he comprehends the norms of social behavior.

The relationship of the child with the world, in fact, arises long before his birth, but only with the emergence of joint activities with parents (then with adults and peers) do these relationships acquire a true source of development of the baby's personality. The child carries out his life activity thanks to the presence of these intersecting and interpenetrating systems, two worlds: the world of parents (adults) and the world of children, each of which objectively and subjectively affects the social and emotional development of the child.

The foundations for a favorable socio-emotional development of the baby are laid during infancy. At an early age, emotional compatibility arises in the "adult-child" dyad. Meaningful, emotionally warm relationships between a parent and a child lead an infant already in the first year of life to a positively colored perception of the environment, to "trust in the world". In order for these qualities to remain leading throughout preschool childhood, parents need to constantly provide the child with psychological, including emotional support, and avoid rigidly regulated living conditions for the child. This has a positive effect on the development of the individual and is a kind of prevention of neurosis and other mental disorders.

At the age of three, the child distinguishes himself from the world around him, proclaiming: "I myself!". The formation of the child's self-awareness begins, the consistent formation of various components of its structure. During this period, it is very important for parents to make efforts to further consolidate the positive self-perceptions of the child and the formation of the first ideas about himself: Who am I? What am I? The child is able to distinguish between the simplest emotional states (sadness, joy, fear, calmness) and already understand their causes. He simply begins to understand the meaning of loneliness and mutual assistance. At the older preschool age, the child is able to "look" deeper into his inner world, to

realize his characteristics and desires with the help of his parents, to learn to defend his opinion, make choices, and purposefully achieve goals in activities. On the basis of self-knowledge, he develops the ability to self-regulate his behavior in accordance with socially accepted norms in society. By demonstrating his own dignity, the child in practice is able to respect another, understand his condition, and show sympathy. The child develops a positive self-esteem as the basis for self-affirmation at the next social stage of development and as a result of the normal course of mental development [3].

For the social - emotional development of the baby in a family environment, it is very important that parents not only provide him with emotional comfort, but also focus more deeply on his psychology, internal problems, problems in relationships with peers, enrich his social experience, make contact with other areas. social development of the child. Their active interaction acts as a necessary condition for this development, and the lifestyle of the family and the educational activity of parents are its important factors. To enrich the child's social and emotional development, it is advisable to create conditions in the family in which the child could actively learn all the most important components of social experience: axiological (value), cognitive, communicative and behavioral - activity.

The social and emotional development of the child is carried out favorably, provided that all components of social experience are "represented" in the family in interconnection with the maximum possible independence of the child in their development. Thus, the inclusion of the value component forms the orientation of the child in the universal values of goodness, beauty, justice, in the value of his family. Values colored with positive feelings are accepted by the child as personally significant and become part of his motivational motives for behavior and interaction with others.

In the process of interaction between individuals, he not only implements existing social relations, but also creates relations. Individual relations of people cannot be understood separately from social relations. Individual relationships are related to the nature of the influence of the social system. In the social relations of individuals that take shape at different levels of society, the objective social laws of the development of society are manifested to one degree or another, each person in one way or another influences the formation of social systems at different levels. As a result, people are always faced with the need to reconcile the values and norms acquired in one area of activity with the requirements in another area. Norms and values accepted in one environment do not correspond to another environment.

In society, a person can be considered as a socio-historical value, and its elements are constantly evolving, interacting, forming a system. It is the interaction of these elements. Belief refers to a person's attitude to the systems that are formed in the system of social relations. It is the degree of formation of beliefs in a person that is important for sociological research. Because depending on the level of faith formed in a person, knowledge of the goals and objectives of his actions in the process of activity. A person manifests his social characteristics with the help of his beliefs.

The link between society and individual goals can be one or another social system. The process that occurs through the assimilation of elements of culture, social norms and human values by society and various types of social communities is called socialization. From how the individual becomes an element of social organization, depends, on the one hand, the formation of the ability of social organization to influence the individual, and on the other hand, the formation of the individual's ability to be under the influence of other people.

The process of personality socialization can be divided into two stages: social adaptation and social internalization. The first is the adaptation of the individual to social conditions, functions, social norms, social groups, organizations and institutions, that is, the environment. The process of social adaptation basically begins and takes shape in the family. Any relationship in the family is reflected in the process of socialization of the individual, so the family plays the main role in the formation of the individual as a person. The second is the process of entry of social norms and values into the inner world of the individual. A person does not mix with the social environment, but enters it as an independent unit; in many theories, human socialization is considered only as an object of external influence. These theories are based on the natural essence of man, which changes socially only with the help of socialization; human activity and the biological given to him; features are not taken into account. Socialization is based on the fact that a person as a social worker is a factor that determines both his own and social conditions and situations of life. Man is the object and subject of social influence. The sign system is important in the process of socialization. With the help of symbols, society controls the activities of individuals. In order for an individual to be able to carry out social activities, he must master the symbols accepted in the social community and the ways of using them. The individual is a functioning being. He does not just react to the external environment, but in the process of practical activity he understands both the objective laws of the external environment and the laws of his development and activity as a person, and on the basis of this

understanding he determines his social activity. . The management of one's activities by a person requires not only knowledge of objective and subjective laws, but also knowledge of these laws, forms and properties of elements under certain conditions.

The cognitive component of social experience informs the child about the norms and methods of behavior and relationships accepted in society, forms of expression of feelings and emotions[4].

The communicative and behavioral-activity components help the child to master the variety of forms of social interaction, cooperation, using verbal and non-verbal means of communication, as well as cultural forms and ways of behavior and activities that allow the child to actively express their feelings and desires. According to domestic scientists, social and emotional development is carried out constantly, permeates all the life of a child in a family. In modern scientific approaches, it is considered that the internal driving force of social and emotional development is the satisfaction of the leading social needs of the child. These include:

- The need for emotionally positive contacts, for love and a benevolent attitude, which creates a child a sense of security and a sense of the value of his personality, the desire for self-realization.
- The need for active various activities and creativity, the satisfaction of this need stimulates positive self-affirmations, forms a sense of confidence.
- The need for recognition of the child's achievements by the parents, which forms a positive self-esteem, self-esteem and encourages the child to actively, positively directed expression of his feelings to the world.
- The need for knowledge and active information exchange, which contributes to the development of intellectual emotions, the joy of discovery and cognitive activity of the child.
- The need for active, meaningful and varied communication of the child with adults and children, which develops social feelings, cooperation, the ability to express themselves in interaction with others and regulate their feelings in the process of communication.

The degree of satisfaction of these needs is determined by the conditions in which the child lives and develops, that is, the environment. As you know, the closest social environment of the child is the family. The environmental approach of the family in education is one of the most popular today. The environment acts as a generalized, cumulative, unified, integral means. The quality of the environment

depends on the interaction, interpenetration and mutual enrichment of factors and conditions.

A home subject-spatial developing environment is considered as a necessary condition for the life of a child. Built taking into account the personality-oriented approach to the child, the developing environment ensures the development and formation of the most important qualities in his personality. The environment for the development of the child is the space of the life of a preschooler, the conditions in which his life proceeds.

Subject-spatial environment of development - the organization of space and the use of equipment and other equipment in accordance with the goals of safety, the psychological well-being of the child and his development.

The educational environment, according to researchers L.I. Novikova, Yu.S. Manuilov, is a means of developing the personality of a child. The environment has such basic parameters as activity and consistency. There is not a single component of the environment that would not have its own significance in the process of influencing a person. Another researcher of the environment (E.V. Bondarevskaya) emphasizes the need to treat it as "the living space of the child, where education is carried out by life itself, events and relationships in which it is involved" [5].

The main purpose of the educational environment in the family is to contribute to the development and formation of the personality of the baby. One of the latest approaches to understanding the environment defines it as an "environment of interaction" (a generalization at a higher level of the environment of activity, the environment of communication and the environment of relations) [6].

In recent decades, psychologists have made a number of remarkable discoveries. One of them is about the importance of the style of communication with the child for the development of his personality. Relationships between family members, personal example of fathers and mothers, family traditions - all this can be summed up in one word - communication. Communication between older and younger in the family has three forms: emotional - affection, care, tenderness; situational - contact of adults with the child in the game, entertainment; speech - disclosure of norms of behavior, advice, expression of sympathy. These forms almost always appear in unity.

Now it has become an indisputable truth that communication is as necessary for a child as food. If we continue the comparison with food, then we can say that communication can be not only healthy, but also harmful. Bad food poisons the

body; incorrect communication "poisons" the child's psyche, endangers his psychological health, emotional well-being, and subsequently, of course, his fate.

World practice has shown that even very difficult problems of upbringing are completely solvable if it is possible to restore a favorable style of communication in the family. In any of the most difficult and acute pedagogical situations, parents should reckon with the self-esteem of the little man, see him as a developing personality, strive for mutual understanding based on respect and trust, and be fair in assessing his actions; in their requirements for the child always remain friendly. How important for us is the emotional well-being of children, their confidence in the future, in the future happy life. Common joy, joint work, caring, living connection with children greatly develop the feeling of the family. This is the microenvironment of the development of the child, which gives him spiritual comfort. These are the components without which there are no conditions for the development of a full-fledged person.

Education is a multifaceted, holistic process, carried out constantly and continuously, and therefore requires an integrated approach.

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